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MECHANISM OF COMMUNICATION RELATIONS BETWEEN SUBJECTS OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC ORGANIZATIONS

МЕХАНІЗМ КОМУНІКАЦІЙНИХ ВІДНОСИН СУБ'ЄКТІВ ЗОВНІШНЬОЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ ТА МІЖНАРОДНИХ ЕКОНОМІЧНИХ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙ

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Левкіна Р.В., Котко Я.М., Кулініч О.А. Механізм комунікаційних відносин суб'єктів зовнішньоекономічної діяльності та міжнародних економічних організацій. Науково-методична стаття.

Мета публікації полягає у розробці механізму комунікаційних відносин суб'єктів зовнішньоекономічної діяльності і міжнародних економічних організацій. Зроблено висновок про його базисну структуру, яка представляє собою сукупність інформаційних потоків між ними і міжнародними організаціями з обов'язковим зворотнім зв'язком, підлягає впливу з боку зовнішнього середовища, враховує внутрішню організаційну структуру суб'єктів бізнесу, функціонує на принципах прозорості, стратегічності й розвитку, партнерства, толерантності, об'єктивності, оперативності і своєчасності реагування, креативності та ін. Результати наукового дослідження мають теоретико-методичний і практичний характер, використання запропонованого механізму комунікаційних відносин дозволяє підвищити ефективність комунікаційної політики суб'єктів ЗЕД, забезпечити власний подальший розвиток, розвиток національної економіки і опосередковано впливати на розвиток світової економіки у цілому.

Ключові слова: комунікаційні відносини, суб'єкти зовнішньоекономічної діяльності, механізм відносин, міжнародні економічні організації, підприємницькі структури

Levkina R.V., Kotko Ya.M., Kulinich O.A. Mechanism of Communication Relations Between Subjects of Foreign Economic Activity and International Economic Organizations. Scientific and methodical article.

The purpose of the publication is to develop a mechanism of communication relations between subjects of foreign economic activity and international economic organizations. It is concluded that its basic structure is a set of information flows between them and international organizations with mandatory feedback, subject to influence from the external environment, considering the internal organizational structure of business entities, operating on the principles of transparency, strategic and development, partnership, tolerance, objectivity, efficiency and timeliness of response, creativity, etc. The results of the scientific research are theoretical, methodological and practical in nature; the use of the proposed mechanism of communication relations allows to increase the effectiveness of the communication policy of foreign economic operators, to ensure their own further development, the development of the national economy and indirectly influence the development of the world economy as a whole.

Keywords: communication relations, subjects of foreign economic activity, mechanism of relations, international economic organizations, business structures

At the current stage of development of the global economy, foreign economic operators are forced to operate under the influence of rapidly changing qualitative and quantitative factors. Changes are also taking place in the internal environment of enterprises. This is due to the rapid processes of transition to a new technological system, where information is a factor of influence and is both a commodity and a factor of production. One of the forms of using information to solve the problems of strategic development of an enterprise is communication relations. Such relations form the basis for effective functioning by mutually coordinating their own interests and the interests of other entities. Given the complication of interaction in foreign markets, high level of competition and specific methods of activity regulation, communication relations are becoming increasingly relevant for scientific research. Moreover, communication is also developing in the direction of cooperation with international economic organizations, which, on the one hand, create the basis for close cooperation, and on the other hand, require strict compliance with international agreements. It should be noted that functioning within a certain framework has positive results, since strict compliance with the rules and ensuring production standards actually simplify the functioning of foreign economic activity. In such conditions, communication relations become a kind of "bridge" between different subjects of foreign economic activity, including international organi-

zations that carry out foreign economic activity and regulate it at the same time. The mechanism of communication relations actually ensures effective cooperation between them.

Analysis of recent research and publications

A large list of scientific publications is devoted to the problems of development of foreign economic activity entities, the authors of which are: S.V. Bestuzheva [1], V.F. Tyshchenko [2], V.M. Ostapenko, K.P. Boldovska [3] and others. The publication of I.I. Havryliuk is devoted to the analysis of factors influencing Ukraine's foreign trade, human capital, and socio-economic infrastructure [4]. The study by V.V. Zelich and M.E. Matveev [5] is devoted to the peculiarities of regulating foreign economic activity under martial law. R. Skrynkovskiy [6], O. Protseviat, N. Pavlenchuk, and S. Tsiukha concluded that martial law had a negative impact on the trends in the development of foreign economic activity of the country and its entities due to numerous barriers to export trade. S.V. Skrypnyk, O.S. Protseviat and O.V. Voronova focused on the current circumstances in the country, which force the subjects to form such mechanisms for the implementation of foreign economic activity that allow combining tools to stimulate international activity and ensure the coordination of current and strategic results [7].

Increasing interdependence of global market participants in the context of socio-economic and political ties, gives rise to contradictions and contradictions, the resolution of which can be resolved through the establishment of communication mechanisms that allow them to harmonize their interests and back them up with signed international agreements. It is through communication mechanism, the country's integration into the global and regional economies, as well as cooperation with international economic organizations.

V.V. Latsysheva and V.O. Babina studied the international image of Ukraine, communications with international organizations in the pre-war period and offered their own proposals on the directions and prospects of cooperation [8]. According to O.B. Demianiuk, providing Ukraine with international financial assistance under martial law allows to support the national economy, ensure the protection of territorial integrity and solve social problems of the population [9]. The experience of other countries that have been in a similar situation in different years is invaluable in terms of building a national development strategy. Even in the agricultural sector, there is an opportunity to introduce the best foreign practices of joint and several liability of business entities to the population [10].

Despite numerous scientific publications, the issues of methodology and practice of organizing communication relations of foreign economic activity entities in the international business environment have not been sufficiently studied. Most publications focus on the criterion issues of assessing the effectiveness of foreign economic activity at the micro and macro levels. The problems of relations between foreign economic entities and international organizations and governing

bodies of international integration associations remain unaddressed. The problems can be partially solved by developing and implementing a mechanism of communication relations that performs the functions of regulation, control, management and stimulation of such relations. And although the prerogative in this regard belongs to the governments of countries that communicate with each other and with international organizations, foreign economic operators implement the country's foreign policy in practice, compete in world markets and influence their conditions. The economic and administrative methods of regulation, the choice of tools for certain forms of international economic relations are aimed at foreign economic operators. No studies have been conducted on the effectiveness of the communication mechanism and its impact on the country's export potential and economic openness strategy. Thus, the development of a mechanism for communication relations between foreign economic operators and international economic organizations is relevant in the context of its impact on the efficiency and further development of the national economy.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The results of our previous studies are the basis for considering the theoretical and practical issues covered in this article related to the development of a mechanism of communication relations at the macro level. Thus, in [10], attention is focused on the experience of agricultural enterprises of other countries in using the principles of joint and several liability in planning production and sales activities and partnerships with consumers, and in [11] – on the peculiarities of cooperation with a trading partner country. In [12], we studied the prerequisites for the formation and development of the export potential of domestic business entities. Based on an integrated approach, we evaluated the effectiveness of the sales activities of domestic enterprises in foreign markets, which showed its ability to solve problems of this class. From the point of view of ease of use, traditional methods of studying the efficiency of foreign economic activity entities and their adaptation to the changing environment of integration and globalization processes, as well as issues of economic security, continue to be interesting [13, 14]. At the same time, economic diplomacy plays an important role, as its principles form the basis of business communications in foreign markets. The results of the study of trends in international technology transfer and their importance for sectoral entrepreneurship and the national economy as a whole are published in [15, 16]. The present publication is a logical continuation of our research in the field of international economic relations and foreign economic activity of business structures.

The aim of the article is to develop a mechanism for communication relations between foreign economic entities and international economic organizations. To achieve this goal, the author sets the following tasks: to identify global challenges and trends in the development of the world economy in the context of building a new technological structure and a system of factors of influence on domestic entities engaged in

foreign economic activity; to analyze the results of cooperation between specific international economic organizations and Ukraine, and to determine the areas of financial and non-financial support for business structures; to analyze theoretical and methodological developments regarding the essence and structure of the mechanism of communication relations and micro- and macro-level factors, development of the structure of the mechanism of communication relations between subjects of foreign economic activity and international economic organizations, formulation of certain provisions for the implementation of the mechanism in practice.

The main part

The foreign economic activity of domestic business entities takes place in an environment influenced by integration and globalization processes and characterized by a high level of bipolarity, intensified competitive and political struggle for raw materials and sales markets. At the same time, changes in the internal environment of enterprises, relocation to a new location and the need to build business communications with new partners, and access to new sales markets complicate management processes. The requirements to find the best options for further development of the enterprise and to make the "only right decision" are increasing, which raises doubts in terms of its definition and implementation. The relationship between Ukraine and international organizations continues to be complicated, as the country is at the stage of building economic and political independence. This requires increased attention not only to the issues of production and trade in world markets, but also to the problems of communication with representatives of international business, international economic organizations, and integration associations. These problems undoubtedly have an impact on foreign economic operators, complicating and at the same time creating favorable conditions for their rapid development in case of adaptation to changes and development of their own strategy. Fig. 1 schematically presents the mechanism of functioning of domestic foreign economic entities in the world market, identifies global challenges and trends, factors of macroeconomic influence, threats and opportunities in domestic and foreign markets [1, 2].

The support of Ukraine and its constituent entities by international organizations and integration associations is not uniform. They have divided into those that have openly demonstrated political and economic solidarity (PACE, OSCE, EU, G7, NATO) and those that have declared political and diplomatic isolation of the aggressors and large-scale restrictions on their participation in their own structures. At the same time, problems came to the surface, the need to solve which proved the inability and incompetence of international organizations [6]. Solving most of the global problems that currently exist in the world requires a preparatory period, the main task of which is to establish business communications between countries and organizations. Thus, the establishment of communication processes requires the introduction of

an effective communication mechanism that considers the specifics and features of the internal environment at the micro and macro levels, and is focused on global development and changes in the technological structure [7]. In our opinion, it is necessary to start by analyzing Ukraine's effective experience of cooperation with international organizations and identifying positions with potential for the future.

Thus, the signing of the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement within the framework of WTO membership allowed for the creation of a free trade area, the main conditions of which were: abolition of import duties; introduction of uniform methods for determining the country of origin of goods; harmonization of domestic norms, procedures and regulations of production and trade with European standards; introduction of the most favored nation regime; protection of intellectual property rights. The basis for European support for small and medium-sized enterprises through soft loans, microfinance, grants, educational programs, consultations and trainings on starting a business, development of cluster structures, exchange of experience and technologies was formed. The suspension of customs tariffs and anti-dumping duties, global protectionist measures against imports from Ukraine (until 06.06.2024) was recorded and the direction for signing the ACAA Agreement was outlined, according to which Ukrainian technical regulations will comply with EU directives and will have the European CE mark of conformity.

The main business associations operating in the European Union and with which business structures cooperate is the Confederation of European Business. Its influence is felt at the level of competitiveness and business performance. The European Federation of Chambers of Commerce and Industry is concerned with socio-economic progress and the spread of the concept of social entrepreneurship in Europe and the world, while the European Wholesale and Retail Trade Association, the Association of Small and Medium-sized Businesses, and the European Food and Beverage Association are concerned with creating a broad communication environment for business entities. In 2023, the share of trade turnover in Ukraine's total trade reached 56,0%, or 55,9 milliard USD, which is 1,9% more than in 2022 [8].

Potential threats to domestic business include the risk of indirect and direct involvement in global conflicts; relocation of hazardous production to the territory of enterprises; deepening demographic crisis and lack of highly skilled labor due to increased migration and outflow of valuable personnel. The macro-level threat is the loss of Ukraine's political and economic sovereignty, the growing political influence of the EU countries; the difficulty of transition to European standards, foreign economic regime, etc. The effect of these factors (along with other factors of martial law) had the greatest impact on exports of goods to the EU, which decreased by 16,1% and amounted to USD 23,4 milliard in 2023 and an increase in imports to almost 20,5%. Thus, Ukraine's foreign trade balance with the EU countries is negative and amounts to -9.1 milliard USD [9].

Figure 1. Influence of the external environment on the functioning of foreign economic activity
 Source: compiled by authors on materials [3-5]

Ukraine's cooperation and membership in the UN covers a wide range of issues, among which the most important are ensuring peace, prosperity and protection of sovereign interests. That is, the tasks of the UN that were formulated in the founding documents of the organization at its creation. However, we can name a number of issues that are directly related to the functioning of business entities: international cooperation on the dissemination of the Sustainable Development Concept, or rather, areas of joint solution of social problems, economic growth of the poorest countries of the world, and environmental protection. The provision of advisory and financial assistance by specialized United Nations agencies for poverty

eradication and achievement of national sustainable development goals at the macro level involves the creation of favorable conditions for doing business, government regulation, and environmental protection. Since independence, the UN has provided over \$200 million in aid to Ukraine. The United Nations has provided more than \$200 million in assistance to Ukraine for the implementation of more than 300 projects and programs. In addition, under the Framework Program for 2018-2022, USD 667 million was provided. The total amount of assistance was \$667 million. After 2022, cooperation between Ukraine and the UN expanded to the humanitarian sphere (international UN conferences: UNFPA, WHO,

UNICEF, etc.), with humanitarian assistance to the population of Ukraine reaching USD 0,5 milliard. In 2020, humanitarian assistance was provided to about 2 million people and assistance in the implementation of projects and social programs – 158 million dollars USD [17].

Active cooperation between Ukraine and the IMF is developing to achieve macroeconomic stability, implement economic reforms, and share financial and technical resources. Over a long period of time, more than 16 programs of economic development and support for business reforms have been launched with a total value of over USD 54 milliard. The NBU has used a portion of these funds to cover the state budget deficit and the NBU's foreign exchange reserves, as well as to ensure fiscal and financial stability. Implementation of the IMF's instruments of influence, in particular the Rapid Funding Facility and the Extended Fund Facility, a program worth USD 15,6 milliard was implemented. The total amount of support amounted to 115 milliard US dollars [18].

The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development's cooperation with Ukraine is aimed at financing economic reforms to accelerate the transition to a market economy and develop competition through the implementation of targeted lending programs for investment projects and technical assistance projects, consultations, and training of entrepreneurs in foreign economic activity. In 2022, the EBRD implemented an initial €2 milliard «resilience package» that provides funding for measures to help affected businesses and countries: loan deferrals, liquidity support, and trade finance. In 2023, the EBRD allocated €18,1 milliard in 529 projects [19].

Thus, it can be summarized that Ukraine establishes and maintains communication ties with international economic organizations, which result in the creation of preconditions for stabilization, recovery and development of the economy, diversification of the production and sales sector, and development of foreign economic activity of enterprises. Communication links influence the formation of a favorable international climate, the involvement of special incentive instruments for export activities (competitiveness of domestic products in world markets, exchange rate stability, price incentives, measures to minimize the negative impact of currency fluctuations, free economic zones, most favored nation treatment, financial support for exports, compensatory financial measures) and the growth of the share of the high-tech component of the export structure [10-11].

T.M. Burmaka believes that communication links are a set of methods, principles, means and forms of influence on the interaction of business structures, government agencies, scientific organizations in the process of communication to solve tactical and strategic tasks in managing economic relations [20].

Y.S. Hrynychuk and L.P. Khakhula draw attention to the international component of communication relations and consider them to be a set of individuals who constantly interact with each other on the basis of established and functioning information channels [21].

V.P. Kubko considers communication relations from the standpoint of their role in ensuring the effectiveness of foreign economic activity, which depends on the timely exchange of reliable information, the potential for achieving the goals of interaction, the prerequisites for mutual understanding and cooperation [22].

We support the position of these scholars and propose to consider communication relations systematically in combination with appropriate methods and tools through which the subjects of relations influence their objects. Thus, communication relations are a management system that, in addition to the functions of organization, planning, motivation and control, determines the process of understanding, information exchange, and comprehension of interaction. With the help of effective communication methods and a rationally organized process of transferring, assimilating and using information between subjects of international economic relations, certain problems are solved. A condition for the implementation of effective communication links between subjects of foreign economic activity and international organizations is the introduction of a communication mechanism of interaction [12].

In his publication, L.R. Prus [23] notes that the communication mechanism is a purposeful managerial impact on the communications of an enterprise. The main forms of practical implementation of the communication mechanism are communication programs and activities, in the process of which resources are consumed and communication processes intersect.

Scientist O.M. Lozovsky [24] expresses a different view and believes that it is the most important tool for managing business relations and a way of transmitting information that helps enterprises develop and strengthen their market positions.

We support both approaches, but at the same time note their limitations. In other words, the communication mechanism functions with the help of innovative tools that mutually coordinate management functions and the effectiveness of their implementation, modern models of foreign economic activity and international institutions. An important function of business communications has always been the analytical function, assessing the external environment using verbal and non-verbal methods that allow to identify deep problems, sometimes even at the level of feelings. In this case, management decisions are more effective, indicators are controlled, and relationships are based on trust and mutual respect. Therefore, we consider the following principles of the mechanism's functioning:

- the principle of transparency – constant regulation of the interaction system, creation of a system of internal and external incentives and motives, connections and results that meet common interests and consider the potential for integration;
- the principle of openness – communication processes are aimed at positive results for the national and global economy, outside of unfair competition and information danger;

- the principle of strategic and developmental approach – considering long-term and short-term plans in the implementation of communications, timely informing about changes, establishing feedback, and reflection to understand the processes of interaction in the future;
- the principle of partnership – establishing interaction through communication with all stakeholders in international economic relations of organizations to determine their needs and common interests, and to make joint decisions;
- the principle of tolerance and objectivity – respect and tolerant attitude to the behavior and decisions of international economic relations actors;
- the principle of efficiency and timeliness – operational analysis, planning, forecasting of communication relations; identification of risks and implementation of measures to influence communication relations in times of crisis;
- the principle of creativity – the use of new styles and means to convey an objective perception of information within the framework of innovative models of relations between subjects of foreign economic activity and international economic organizations [12-14].

The main elements of the mechanism of communication relations, which corresponds to the theoretical and methodological provisions on its creation and functioning, to which we drew attention in this publication earlier, are presented in Fig. 2.

The main directions for the development of such a mechanism, without specifying its subjects by type of activity, business scale, belonging to the economy of a particular country or integration association, are systematic reduction of bureaucracy and corruption, increased transparency in joint activities, strengthening financial discipline, ensuring the integrity of communication subjects, creating preconditions for the growth of communications and expansion of their types, including informal communications. The development of the mechanism of communication between foreign economic operators and international organizations should have a diversified and extensive system to compensate for failures in some types of communication with specific entities with the relations of others, and the positive result of such relations is determined by the effectiveness of relations between different entities and their overall strategic focus on achieving a common result. Of course, it is important for domestic foreign trade entities to reform or at least abolish some taxes during the crisis period to provide additional opportunities to use the income to maintain liquidity and financial stability; introduce tax holidays and digitalize the workflow with government agencies and tax documents. Introducing a most favored nation regime for entrepreneurship, similar to the one in foreign trade, will boost entrepreneurship, develop competition, and facilitate access to foreign markets. The use of state platforms for better communication between business entities, especially those located in other regions of the country or even abroad, will not

only improve communication relations but also identify existing problems, timely identify the likelihood of a crisis or even bankruptcy, and plan the necessary support measures. It is feedback and trust that will come in handy when implementing preventive measures.

As a rule, the process of communication involves the creation of public opinion at the national level. Gradually, domestic PR goes beyond the borders of the country and becomes the basis of international PR, which includes the business reputation of not only foreign economic operators, but also state bodies, the government, and the country as a whole. Information support of international organizations on the foreign economic and investment potential of countries and their entities, interests, potential impact on the international image is the basis for establishing successful cooperation in various areas of foreign economic activity [12].

An important method of influencing communication relations is legal methods of regulating them, the basis for which is compliance with the regulatory framework, the system of international agreements within the framework of international trade organizations, etc. Such an organization is the World Trade Organization and previous signed agreements on the introduction of tariffs in trade in goods and services (GATT, GATS and other specialized agreements). The organization's activities are aimed at liberalizing trade, eliminating unreasonable trade barriers, reducing customs duties and introducing common international trade standards and rules. Thus, trade discrimination is eliminated, protectionist measures, dumping and other manifestations of unfair competition, which are difficult to identify and prove in an arbitration court, are eliminated. Therefore, long-term communication, mutually beneficial relations, trust and the formation of business reputation may be the only leverage to influence relations and the content of cooperation policy. In some cases, the unification of the regulatory framework for foreign economic activity leads to a gradual convergence of national economies, overlapping interests, adaptation and joint development. Conditions are being created for new international economic integration associations [13].

Our proposed structure of the mechanism of communication relations between global economic actors, including business entities operating in foreign markets and international organizations, ensures the development of partnerships based on the strategic interests of all participants. Of course, it is impossible to identify and prevent all possible conflict situations in the short term, let alone in the long term, since there is always a temptation to win better operating conditions, higher income and wider markets, but such a mechanism, in our opinion, ensures relatively equal rights and obligations of all participants in communication at the international level. High level of responsibility for own actions, transparent relations and partnership allow us to avoid the vast majority of possible risks, conflicts and manipulations.

Figure 2. Mechanism of communication relations between foreign economic operators and international economic organizations.

Source: developed by the authors

A balanced fiscal policy and coordination within the budget process based on international practices of leading countries; establishing alternative ways to resolve disputes in economic relations; harmonization of regulatory requirements and international cooperation; increase the openness of information exchange between foreign economic operators and international organizations to effectively integrate into the global financial market; to stimulate

international the global financial market; to stimulate international technology transfer, ensure cybersecurity in international economic relations.

Conclusion

Thus, in this scientific publication, we have proposed the structure of the mechanism of communication relations between foreign economic operators and international economic organizations. This became possible as a result of the assessment of the impact of global challenges and trends in the

development of the world economy on foreign economic activity, including: the spread of protectionist trends, polycentricity, intensification of competition, weakening of the legal influence of international organizations, digitalization of all sectors of the economy; as well as the identification of factors of influence: instability of the world economy and recession, crisis of regulatory and legal regulation, changes in the structure of the world economy, emergence of new world markets for goods and services, changes in the analysis of the results of cooperation between international economic organizations (UN, IMF, EBRD, WTO, Confederation of European Business, European Federation of Chambers of Commerce and Industry) and Ukraine shows that the areas of financial and non-financial support for the development of domestic business

structures are expanding and that the potential for cooperation is high, especially with active integration into the European market. The proposed mechanism of communication relations for such subjects of foreign economic activity is based on the growth of information flows between them and international organizations with mandatory feedback and further use of the results of communication for their own development and the development of the entire world economy. The results of the scientific research are theoretical, methodological and practical in nature; the use of the proposed mechanism of communication relations allows to increase the efficiency of communication policy of foreign economic operators, to ensure their own further development, development of the national economy and indirectly influence the development of the world economy as a whole.

Abstract

The purpose of the article is to develop a mechanism for communication relations between subjects of foreign economic activity and international economic organizations. To achieve this goal, the author sets the following tasks: to identify global challenges and trends in the development of the world economy in the context of building a new technological structure and a system of factors of influence on domestic entities engaged in foreign economic activity; to analyze the results of cooperation between specific international economic organizations and Ukraine, and to determine the areas of financial and non-financial support for business entities; to analyze theoretical and methodological developments regarding the essence and structure of the mechanism of communication relations and As a result of the research, the authors came to the conclusion that the impact of global challenges and trends in the world economy on foreign economic activity and the efficiency of its subjects is increasing. The main challenges are identified as: the spread of protectionist tendencies, polycentricity, increased competition, weakening of the legal influence of international organizations, and the trend is the transition to a new technological system, accompanied by the processes of digitalization of all sectors of the economy and all countries of the world without exception. The author identifies the factors of influence, including the instability of the global economy and recession, the crisis of regulatory and legal regulation, changes in the structure of the global economy, the emergence of new global markets for goods and services, and changes in the directions of trade flows. The analysis of the results of cooperation between international economic organizations (UN, IMF, EBRD, WTO, Confederation of European Business, European Federation of Chambers of Commerce and Industry) and Ukraine shows that the areas of financial and non-financial support for the development of domestic business structures are expanding and that the potential for cooperation is high in the future, especially with active integration into the European market. The mechanism of communication relations for such subjects of foreign economic activity is proposed and a conclusion is made about its basic structure, which is a set of information flows between them and international organizations with mandatory feedback, is subject to influence from the external environment, takes into account the internal organizational structure of business entities, functions on the principles of transparency, strategic and development, partnership, tolerance, objectivity, efficiency and timeliness of response, creativity, and is based on the principles of communication policy of foreign economic activity. The results of the scientific research are theoretical, methodological and practical in nature, the use of the proposed mechanism of communication relations allows to increase the effectiveness of the communication policy of foreign economic activity entities, to ensure their own further development, the development of the national economy and indirectly influence the development of the world economy as a whole.

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